

Post-Quantum Blockchain-Based Decentralized Identity Management for Resource Sharing in Open Radio Access Networks

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Abstract

Blockchain Network (BCN)-based Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) has recently surfaced as an identity and access management framework that allows users and organizations to control over their data. On the other hand, Open Radio Access Networks (O-RANs) propose a framework for facilitating the exchange of infrastructure-related data. This study presents the critical role of BCN-SSI in the O-RAN system architecture and promises an authentication process to provide insights into the robust security measures

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used to seamlessly establish the identification of users and entities within the O-RAN ecosystem in the post-quantum era. We show that the integration of BCN-SSI enhances security protocols and ensure the integrity of communication networks in the evolving technological landscape. As an illustrative use case, spectrum sharing, is also presented to demonstrate the practicality and the impact of the proposed framework. Furthermore, we address the potential threats posed by quantum attacks on BCN-based SSI systems by investigating Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC). Simulation results confirm the effectiveness of the proposed BCN-based DIM and emphasize its role in securing identity management processes within the O-RAN context. Finally, we address the use of efficient computational techniques in the context of PQC, which holds significant potential in terms of reducing energy consumption overall.

Index Terms

Self-sovereign identity, blockchain networks, resource sharing, O-RAN, post-quantum.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, significant advances in telecommunications technology have enabled the emergence of open radio access networks (Open Radio Access Networks (O-RANs)). O-RANs bring a paradigm shift by disaggregating traditional monolithic radio access network components to enable greater flexibility, interoperability and innovation in wireless communications deployment [1]. As the importance of O-RANs continues to grow, ensuring secure and reliable identity management for the various entities within the O-RAN ecosystem becomes a major concern. The O-RAN architecture, which is characterized by openness and disaggregation, increases the attack surface and introduces potential vulnerabilities. O-RAN also aims to promote interoperability between different network components and vendors. Thanks to its modular nature, the conventional strategy focuses on avoiding vendor lock-in for intrinsic network security without any decentralization. Appropriate identity management therefore ensures that the various components can communicate with each other securely and seamlessly. Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs) are unique identifiers tied to cryptographic keys, and verifiable credentials are digitally signed claims issued by trusted entities [2].

Users, Mobile Network Operators (MNOs) and device manufacturers can create their DIDs for themselves and their devices participating in the O-RAN ecosystem and obtain verifiable credentials from trusted authorities. This enables secure authentication, supports interoperability and facilitates trust between participants and forms the basis for building Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) systems in the O-RAN that empower users, MNOs and device owners and improve

network security and privacy. Each DID is associated with a DID document that contains relevant information about the entity, such as public keys, authentication mechanisms, service endpoints and other metadata. The DID document is stored and distributed in a decentralized manner so that it is accessible to other participants in the O-RAN ecosystem for verification and validation. DIDs are usually represented as URIs (Uniform Resource Identifiers) and follow the DID specification defined by the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) [3]. DIDs consist of two main components: the DID method and the DID specific identifier. The DID method defines the rules and mechanisms for creation and resolution of DIDs. It defines how DIDs are created, managed and associated with cryptographic keys and other relevant data. The DID-specific identifier is a unique string or series of characters that identifies a specific entity within the selected DID method. By leveraging BCN-based SSI, O-RAN can benefit from a decentralized and secure identity management that enables a more transparent, efficient and user-centric network ecosystem.

Highlighted by the advent of blockchain technology, the authors in [4] develop decentralized, secure, and efficient mechanisms for managing network access and authentication between inherently untrusted network entities. The paper in [5] proposes a blockchain-based identity management and authentication system for mobile networks, where users' identifying information is controlled by the users themselves. In [6], a method is introduced wherein a user can demonstrate their entitlement to access a specific service without disclosing personal information. The authors in [7] propose a secure endogenous wireless access network architecture based on blockchain that includes a communication plane and a blockchain plane, the latter including blockchain networks and their applications. The application of Blockchain Network (BCN)-based SSI was performed in our previous work [8] and proposed in the context of vehicular networks. The paper in [9] proposes a blockchain-based identity and access management system for Internet of Things (IoT) – especially for smart vehicles – as an example application and shows two interoperable blockchains, Ethereum and Hyperledger Indy, as well as a SSI model.

In the context of the application of BCN in O-RAN, the authors in [10] propose the integration of blockchain technology to enable mobile operators and other actors to autonomously and dynamically exchange Radio Access Network (RAN) resources (e.g. infrastructure) in the form of Virtual Network Functions (VNFs). A blockchain-enabled RAN and decentralized, privacy-preserving Peer-to-Peer (P2P) communication system with secure identity management through mutual authentication is investigated in [11]. Robust verification and validation procedures are

essential for SSI management O-RAN to ensure the authenticity and integrity of digital identities. Verification uses cryptographic techniques to validate the legitimacy of identification information and credentials. In combination with a public-private key infrastructure, entities can authenticate themselves with DIDs without disclosing any third-party information. O-RAN nodes can present verifiable credentials issued by trusted sources, and recipients can verify the data using cryptography to confirm its accuracy and authenticity. These procedures allow users to disclose only the information required for verification, which reduces the risk of identity fraud and improves data protection. By ensuring that credentials and DIDs follow established standards and protocols, validation in SSI enables interoperability between different platforms and services. Blockchain technology, which provides an immutable ledger where DIDs and cryptographic proofs are stored, is essential to this component. Due to this decentralized method, identity data is not subject to the authority of a single party, which increases security and resistance to tampering. Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC) comprises cryptographic algorithms that are designed to be secure against attacks from quantum computers. The cryptographic strength of these algorithms depends on mathematical problems that are believed to be difficult for quantum computers. The Shor algorithm, a quantum algorithm, can factorize large numbers efficiently (in polynomial time) and solve the discrete logarithm problem [12], which forms the basis for the security of widely used classical cryptographic methods such as Rivest–Shamir–Adleman (RSA) and Elliptic-Curve Cryptography (ECC).

A. Related Work

The BCN serves as a base layer that enables secure, decentralized and transparent sharing of resources among MNOs in an O-RAN architecture [10], [13]. The article in [14] investigates the aspects of integrating blockchain in 6G with O-RAN. It creates trust, facilitates secure transactions, ensures the integrity of identity and transaction data and thus increases overall efficiency and effectiveness. The paper in [15] designs a smart contract for multi-player network sharing that enables the automation of RAN sharing processes. However, those papers do not integrate with BCN-based SSI and do not have a PQC adaptation framework. In blockchain-based network sharing, spectrum sharing and resource allocation is a widely studied aspect. The article in [16] gives an overview of the state of the art in blockchain-enabled spectrum allocation and network slicing as well as their implementation challenges related to B5G and 6G network requirements. Similarly, spectrum resources of IoT devices in multiple dimensions can enable reliable and

secure random access to a large amount of terminal data via blockchain as presented in [17]. Finally, the article in [18] investigates and explores the suitability of the application of various blockchain platforms to radio spectrum management, especially focusing on dynamic spectrum sharing applications. In [19], the blockchain radio access network for resource sharing and trading is established as a unified architecture with improved efficiency, security, compatibility and flexibility. The study in [20] presents a blockchain-enabled accountable and transparent infrastructure sharing architecture. However, these solutions does not exploit the potential of decentralized identity management frameworks in the context of PQC era.

Furthermore, the study of PQC algorithms and computational methods addresses a critical aspect of securing attacks against quantum computers [21], [22]. In [23], the authors propose a system that facilitates data sharing among multiple entities via a private PQC blockchain. A post-quantum signature scheme (based on the Dilithium signature scheme) for the transaction signing and verification process of the blockchain is proposed in [24]. However, existing works have primarily focused on the vulnerability of cryptographic systems to quantum attacks within BCNs and has not addressed ensuring the robustness of O-RANs using BCN-based SSI systems. The literature on PQC serves as a foundation for our investigation of securing identity management processes in the O-RAN context and positions this research within the broader discourse on quantum-resistant cryptographic techniques. Our paper provides insights into possible workflow improvements and emphasizes the need for a post-quantum approach in such scenarios. Our previous work in [25] investigated the BCN-based SSI applied to the O-RAN architecture. However, the methodology was not numerically evaluated and a post-quantum extension of the considered methodology was not considered.

B. Our Contributions

Each of the above approaches offers different alternatives for identity management, either as a stand-alone solution or in conjunction with other methodologies. Subsequent research on the integration of O-RAN with BCN in the existing literature relies on the capabilities of BCN as Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) [28]. However, a platform embedded in the SSI for the reliable sharing of resources (e.g. spectrum, network capacity, infrastructure components, etc.) between users and operators in the O-RAN architecture that can simultaneously provide confidentiality, integrity and authentication is missing. Resource sharing can enable more efficient use of network infrastructure, cost savings for operators and fair competition. Note that O-RAN

TABLE I
SUMMARY OF LITERATURE ON IDENTITY MANAGEMENT WITH BLOCKCHAIN IN RESOURCE SHARING AND O-RAN DOMAIN

Reference	Author	Year	Approach	Key Contributions			
				BCN/ SSI	PQC Comp.	BCN O-RAN	Resource Sharing
[16] [17]	Muntaha et al. Sun et al	2023 2021	- Blockchain-enabled spectrum allocation and/or network slicing.	✓			
[21], [23], [22]	- Zeydan et al., - Malina et al.,	- 2022, - 2023	- Post-quantum blockchain-supported data sharing - Review security recommendations, libraries, and the support of PQC	✓	✓		
[26] [27]	- Garzon et al., - Naik et al.	- 2022, - 2020	- Potential of SSI in the context of decentralized system - Offer privacy, user-centricity, and interoperability	✓			
[20], [19]	- Faisal et al., - Le et al.	- 2022, - 2023	- Accountability and transparency for infrastructure sharing. - Resource sharing and trading in blockchain radio access network	✓			✓
[10], [14]	- Giuppon et al., - Xu et al.	- 2022, - 2023	- A novel O-RAN-based blockchain-supported architecture - Potentials of blockchain for resource management and sharing in 6G			✓	✓
[25]	- Zeydan et al.	- 2023	Benefits of resource sharing using O-RAN and BCN SSI		✓	✓	✓
Our paper	Zeydan et al.		Integration of postquantum blockchain-based SSI and resource sharing in O-RAN	✓	✓	✓	✓

is a complex and evolving ecosystem for open and intelligent radio access networks and the integration of new technologies such as BCN-based SSI must be aligned with the objectives of O-RAN. Therefore, in this paper, we propose a BCN-based SSI-embedded O-RAN architecture and a design approach for the resource sharing process. To the best of the authors' knowledge, this is the first work that introduces a post-quantum BCN-based SSI to investigate the identity management and authentication of users or MNOs for a resource sharing scenario in a typical O-RAN architecture model. We also outline the potential limitations and possible solutions for

the application of BCN-based SSI to improve the security, privacy, trust and interoperability of O-RANs in the post-quantum era. The main contributions of the paper can be summarized as follows:

- *Secure and Efficient Identity Management in O-RAN:* We present a robust post-quantum BCN-based SSI tailored for open radio access networks (O-RAN) that ensures secure and efficient identity verification processes within the dynamic and decentralized O-RAN ecosystem.
- *Resilience Against Quantum Threats:* We address the potential threats posed by quantum attacks on BCN-based SSI systems and investigate and utilise PQC computational method. The framework's resilience to quantum threats is detailed and a secure foundation for identity management in the post-quantum era is proposed.
- *Practical Implementation and Considerations:* Simulation results are used to validate the effectiveness of the proposed post-quantum BCN-based SSI approach and to emphasize its practical importance and central role in securing identity management processes in O-RAN. The comprehensive discussion also included implementation results, the integration of computational techniques into the PQC framework, and important considerations regarding the energy consumption of PQC, offering valuable insights for future improvements.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: In Section II we present possible applications of Distributed Identity Management (DIM) in the O-RAN architecture and the entities involved in O-RAN and BCN. Section III presents the crucial steps of the authentication process. In Section IV, we present a use case example of spectrum sharing. Section V details quantum attacks on BCN-based SSI. Section VI provides numerical results. Section VII discusses numerical results and highlights some of the limitations of the proposed approach and possible solutions. Finally, Section VIII presents the conclusions of the paper.

II. THE ROLE OF BCN IN O-RAN

A. Integrating DIM in Open RAN

DIM and resource sharing in O-RAN can provide multiple ways to maintain control over the use of shared and non-shared resource data with third parties. DIDs are typically associated with cryptographic keys to ensure secure authentication and data integrity [26]. The participants of the O-RAN ecosystem, such as users and operators as well as device owners, generate public-private key pairs. The public key is included in the DID document associated with the DID (which can

Fig. 1: BCN-based SSI and BCN enabled RAN sharing.

be stored in BCN), while the private key is securely stored by the corresponding entity [27]. This key pair enables cryptographic operations such as signing and verification to establish trust and secure interactions within the O-RAN network.

The application of DIM is an open topic in O-RAN and a solution based on DLTs can be very powerful. A BCN-based SSI in an O-RAN architecture for equipment management or resource sharing can help to overcome some of the limitations. First of all, in the context of O-RAN, a specific DID method needs to be defined to support the unique requirements of the ecosystem. The DID method for O-RAN should consider aspects such as scalability, interoperability and integration with existing identity systems. The method defines the processes and protocols for creating, updating and resolving DIDs within the O-RAN environment.

B. System Architecture

A promising approach to ensure identity management and trust for network management operations during resource sharing (e.g., Radio Units (RUs), Distributed Units (DUs), or Central Units (CUs) in O-RAN) and data exchange between entities (e.g., users, MNOs, or regulators) in an O-RAN architecture is the use of DLTs such as BCN and SSI. Fig. 1 shows BCN-based SSI and BCN enabled system for RAN sharing scenario for multiple operator scenario. In this

architecture, RAN resources (in O-RU) are shared by two operators (namely MNO-1 and MNO-2), and requests to Radio Intelligence Controller (RIC) are executed by vertical slicers of each operator. Inside O-Cloud, there exists O-RAN control, management and orchestration entities, namely vertical slicers (that request network slice service management tasks done by verticals), Service Management and Orchestration (SMO) (that includes RIC), O-DU and O-CU.

For resource sharing among multiple MNOs (or users) in O-RANs while relying on SSI, BCNs can play a critical role in providing the underlying infrastructure for secure and decentralized operations (e.g. see its usage in [29], [30] for cellular networks). The BCN serves as a decentralized ledger where SSIs of users and MNOs (as well as logs related to the resource sharing process in a separate BCN) are stored. Each user/MNO is assigned a unique identity by an issuer in the form of a cryptographic key pair so that they can control and manage their identity information. In such a configuration, the BCN-based SSI ensures the integrity and immutability of the identity data and prevents tampering or unauthorized changes. The BCN provides enhanced security and privacy for the SSIs and sensitive information exchanged between MNOs.

Resource sharing logs in BCN: As MNOs negotiate and interact with each other during resource sharing process (e.g. for spectrum sharing), the BCN also records all transactions and agreements in a transparent and immutable manner (e.g. in a separate chain in this paper as given in Fig. 2). Each interaction between users and MNOs can be recorded on the blockchain or a distributed ledger. These records can include details such as the type of resource accessed, the duration of usage, and the identities of the involved parties. This provides an auditable history of resource sharing activities, ensuring trust and accountability among the participating operators. By having an immutable and transparent audit trail, it becomes easier to detect any anomalies or suspicious behavior during the resource sharing process. The immutable records also help resolve disputes or conflicts, if any. The BCN employs a consensus mechanism, such as proof-of-work or proof-of-stake, to validate and agree upon the state of the shared ledger. Consensus ensures that all network participants reach a consensus on the order and validity of transactions, preventing fraudulent or malicious activities.

Integration aspects: The integration of O-RAN with BCN can be achieved by a module or layer that interacts with the BCN to store and retrieve O-RAN infrastructure data in a secure and transparent manner. A secure data exchange between O-RAN entities and BCN can be achieved with a secure communication protocol which ensures only the desired data can be stored in the BCN, excluding all private data. Smart contract-based trust verification provides

proof of trust through the BCN by verifying the authenticity and integrity of the data exchanged between entities. On the other hand, permissioned BCN can also be utilized to ensure privacy by selecting only authorized entities e.g., MNOs, infrastructure and service providers, network equipment vendors, regulatory bodies, authorized third parties or validators to participate in the consensus process and update the ledger within the BCN. Access control mechanisms and encryption techniques can be implemented to protect the data in the BCN with reducing the computational overhead and to ensure that only trusted entities are involved inside O-RAN.

Storage and Access Control: DIDs require robust storage and access control mechanisms to manage potentially large volumes of identity data securely. Storage solutions include blockchains for immutability, decentralized file systems like Interplanetary File System (IPFS) for redundancy, and cloud storage with cryptographic anchors for cost-effectiveness. Access control employs cryptographic techniques such as public key infrastructure and zero-knowledge proofs, fine-grained permissions through ACLs, role-based and capability-based access control, and smart contracts for automated enforcement. Secure communication protocols, like end-to-end encryption and DIDAuth, ensure secure interactions, while identity hubs provide personal data stores and access management, balancing scalability, interoperability, and privacy.

C. Users in O-RAN

SSI can be applied to O-RAN in the context of users. *User Authentication and Authorization:* SSI can establish a secure and decentralized identity management system for users accessing O-RAN. Users can have their own SSIs (issued by an issuer), which they can control and manage, allowing for secure authentication and authorization without relying on centralized identity providers. This identity would be unique to them and under their control. It can be implemented using DIDs and verifiable credentials. SSI also empowers individuals to control the sharing of their personal information. Users can choose which attributes of their digital identity to disclose and to whom. Additionally, they can set consent preferences for how their data should be used by operators. For example, a user may consent to share their location data with a specific operator for a limited period. SSI enables fine-grained privacy and consent management, allowing users to maintain control over their data in the resource sharing process.

For equipment and device identity, SSI can be utilized to assign unique and verifiable identities to equipment and devices within the O-RAN ecosystem. Each device can have its own digital identity, enabling secure communication, authentication, and tracking of devices throughout the

network. For *trust and reputation management*, SSI can play a crucial role in establishing trust and reputation mechanisms within the O-RAN environment. By leveraging SSI, users in the network can verify and validate the identity, history, and reputation of other network entities, such as MNOs, service providers, and equipment vendors during resource sharing process in O-RAN architecture using verifiable credentials. These credentials can contain information such as each user or MNO affiliation, certifications, and reputation scores. By verifying the credentials presented by other participants, entities can establish trust and ensure that only authorized and authenticated users and MNOs are allowed to access and share resources. For *secure network access and configuration*, SSI can facilitate secure network access and configuration for authorized entities within the O-RAN ecosystem. For *billing and settlement*, SSI can streamline the billing and settlement processes in O-RAN by providing verifiable and tamper-proof records of network usage, transactions, and agreements. Participants can use their SSIs to securely and transparently engage in billing and settlement activities, reducing disputes and ensuring fair compensation. For *interoperability and roaming*, SSI can enable seamless interoperability and roaming across different O-RAN deployments and networks.

D. MNOs in O-RAN

BCN-based SSI can help to support resource sharing among multiple MNOs in multiple ways:

Identity-Based Resource Allocation: SSI enables MNOs to establish unique and verifiable identities for their resources, such as network infrastructure, spectrum, or computing resources. By assigning SSIs to these resources, MNOs can securely track and manage their availability, capabilities, and usage.

Secure Negotiation and Agreements: SSI provides a secure framework for MNOs to negotiate and establish resource-sharing agreements. Each operator can present their self-sovereign identity along with their resource capabilities and requirements, facilitating transparent and trusted negotiations. Smart contracts can be used to enforce the terms and conditions of resource sharing.

Access Control and Authorization: SSI allows MNOs to control access to their shared resources based on verifiable identities. MNOs can define access policies and permissions tied to SSIs, ensuring that only authorized entities can utilize the shared resources.

This helps maintain security and prevent unauthorized usage. *Auditing and Accountability:* SSI enables transparent auditing and accountability in resource sharing. Each MNO can maintain

a tamper-proof record of resource usage and transactions associated with their self-sovereign identity.

This promotes trust among MNOs and allows for efficient tracking and settlement of resource usage. *Interoperability and Interconnection:* SSI supports interoperability and interconnection between MNOs by providing a decentralized and standardized identity framework. Operators can securely recognize and authenticate each other’s identities, enabling seamless sharing of resources across different networks and deployments.

Fig. 2: Authentication with BCN-based SSI enabled O-RAN design.

III. AUTHENTICATION PROCESS

Fig. 2 provides an overview of the key entities involved in BCN-based SSI. These entities include the SSI BCN, the issuer, the holder, and the verifier. The issuer, such as a regulatory authority responsible for O-RAN services in each country, possesses the authority to create and issue digital credentials, also known as verifiable credentials, to individuals or entities. These credentials contain relevant claims or attributes about the holder and are digitally signed by the issuer using their private key to ensure their authenticity and integrity. The holder, such as a MNOs, receives and possesses the digital credentials issued by the issuer. The holder has complete control over their own credentials and can decide when and how to present them to verifiers. The credentials are securely stored in the holder’s digital wallet or enterprise data

store, protected by cryptography and the holder's private key. The holder has the ability to selectively share specific credentials or attributes with verifiers based on their specific needs or requirements by using cryptography and zero-knowledge proofs, if necessary, enabling them to maintain control over their own data. In the context of our case, the verifier (specifically the RIC in SMO) plays the role of an entity responsible for verifying specific claims or attributes about another entity. When the verifier needs to verify the authenticity or validity of a claim made by the holder, they can request the presentation of relevant credentials or attributes for verification purposes. To establish trust in the credentials, the verifier relies on the cryptographic signatures and integrity of the credentials. By validating the digital signatures and ensuring the integrity of the credentials using the issuer's public key, the verifier can ascertain that the credentials were issued by a trusted issuer and have not been tampered with.

In our system, the RIC in SMO plays a crucial role in the authorization process. In **step 1**, when a holder (such as an MNOs) wishes to access the RAN service, they establish an authenticated channel with the issuer through BCN-based SSI. In **step 2**, the issuer issues a verifiable credential to the holder, including specific terms for the smart contract and the RIC in SMO to refine access policies. These terms may specify authorized time slots, specific parts of RIC in SMO, and more. In **step 3**, the holder presents the credentials to the RIC in SMO (verifier), which is then forwarded to BCN-based SSI. In **step 4**, the RIC in SMO verifies the ownership, authorship, and non-revocation of the credential. Additionally, the verifier checks the credential against a list of access policies set by the issuer. Notably, the smart contract on BCN-based SSI has exclusive invocation properties restricted to the issuer and the RIC in SMO controlled by that smart contract. If authentication fails, the RIC in SMO denies RAN service requests from unauthenticated MNOs or refuses to collaborate with them. In **step 5**, the BCN-based SSI invokes the smart contract on the online BCN to check the RIC in SMO access policies using the presented credentials. The smart contract informs the RIC in SMO about the authorization to write in the BCN. Upon successful authentication, the RIC in SMO initiates RAN services in collaboration with authenticated MNOs, and logs are recorded to the BCN.

IV. AN EXAMPLE USE CASE: SPECTRUM SHARING

In an O-RAN architecture, multiple MNOs can collaborate to efficiently share spectrum resources. In such situations, BCN-based SSI can play a critical role in enabling secure and trusted spectrum sharing by MNOs. By leveraging BCN-based SSI, MNOs can effectively share

spectrum resources, optimize network capacity, and provide better services to their customers in O-RANs. Suppose there are three MNOs, MNO A, MNO B, and MNO C, who want to share their unused spectrum resources to improve network capacity and coverage in a specific geographical area.

To accomplish this, several steps need to be followed:

- *First step* is to establish BCN-based SSI for each MNOs. Here, each MNO creates their SSI using BCN, which includes verifiable credentials and attributes related to their network infrastructure and available spectrum resources. These identities are stored on a decentralized and immutable ledger, ensuring data integrity and privacy.
- *Second step* is to negotiate spectrum sharing agreements. Here, MNOs engage in negotiation using their SSIs. They present their available spectrum resources, quality-of-service (QoS) requirements, and desired terms for sharing. During this process, BCN-based SSI allows for transparent and trusted negotiations, ensuring that all parties can verify the identities and claims of each MNO.
- *Third step* is to verify and grant access. Here, once the spectrum sharing agreements are reached, MNOs can authenticate and authorize each other based on their SSIs. This ensures that only authorized MNOs gain access to shared spectrum resources. Access control policies and permissions tied to SSIs enable seamless and secure resource utilization.
- *The fourth step* is for monitoring and auditing using BCN. Here, MNOs continuously monitor and track the usage of shared spectrum resources. They maintain tamper-proof records of resource allocation, utilization, and transactions associated with their SSIs. This provides transparency, accountability, and facilitates accurate settlement of resource usage among MNOs.
- *The fifth step* is dynamic resource allocation. With BCN-based SSI, MNOs can dynamically allocate and release spectrum resources based on demand and availability. As needs of MNOs change, they can securely update their SSIs with revised resource offerings to ensure efficient use of shared spectrum. Fig. 3 depicts this use case.

V. SECURITY CHALLENGES AND MITIGATIONS ON BCN-BASED SSI

A. Challenges

There are several challenges when integrating BCN-based SSI solutions into O.RAN architecture. Some of the are as follows:

Fig. 3: Workflow of the spectrum sharing use case.

(i) **Smart Contract Vulnerabilities:** Smart contracts used for automatic trust verification and data exchange in blockchain-based systems may have vulnerabilities such as coding errors, logic errors and susceptibility to attacks such as re-entrance.

(ii) **Decentralized Storage Security:** The decentralized storage of DID documents and associated data (e.g. on IPFS or blockchain) can lead to unauthorized access to this data if it is not properly encrypted and managed.

(iii) **Key Management:** The security of DIDs relies heavily on the secure management of cryptographic keys. If private keys are compromised, the corresponding identities can be impersonated.

(iv) **Consensus Mechanism Risks:** Blockchain consensus mechanisms can be vulnerable to attacks such as 51% attacks, where an attacker gains control of the majority of the network's computing power.

(v) **Scalability and Performance Issues:** Blockchain technology can face scalability and performance issues, especially with increasing transaction volumes, which can affect the timeliness of identity verifications.

(vi) **Quantum Attacks:** A SSI system based on blockchain technology aims to give individuals control over their own identity information. Blockchain, with its decentralized and tamper-proof nature, can improve the security and privacy of identity management. However, the potential emergence of quantum computing leads to new challenges and vulnerabilities as given in Fig. 4. Fig. 4 (a) shows the places where Eve can attack the transactions on BCN-SSI with the quantum

computer and Fig. 4 (b) shows how the PQC algorithm prevents Eve's quantum attack.

In a BCN-based SSI system, quantum computing attacks could be a problem in many ways.

- Firstly, most blockchain systems rely on public key cryptography for secure transactions and identity verification. Quantum computers could use the Shor algorithm to break widely used public key cryptographic algorithms such as RSA and ECC. This would allow an attacker to derive private keys from public keys and potentially compromise the integrity and confidentiality of the identity system.
- Secondly, digital signatures are used in blockchain transactions to verify the authenticity of messages and prove ownership of private keys. An attacker with a quantum computer could forge digital signatures by breaking the underlying cryptographic algorithms. This would allow attackers to impersonate users and perform unauthorized transactions.
- Third, blockchain systems rely on consensus mechanisms to agree on the state of the ledger. Quantum computers may be able to manipulate the consensus process, which could lead to double-spending attacks or other malicious activity that undermines the blockchain integrity.
- Fourth, the security of a self-sovereign identity system also depends on secure key management practices. Quantum computers could compromise key generation and storage mechanisms, which would lead to the disclosure of private keys and consequently the compromise of user identities.
- Finally, quantum computers could potentially exploit vulnerabilities in the code of smart contracts (which are self-executing contracts where the terms of the agreement are written directly into the code) or disrupt the execution of these contracts, which could lead to unauthorized transactions or unintended behavior. Hash functions such as SHA-256, which are used to create digital fingerprints of data in the blockchain, are considered more resistant to quantum attacks compared to some public key algorithms [31].

B. Mitigation

Some solutions to mitigate above challenges are as follows:

(i) Smart Contract Security: Rigorous auditing and testing of smart contracts before deployment can mitigate risks. Formal verification methods can also be used to ensure the correctness of the contract logic. In addition, the use of standardized frameworks and libraries with a strong security track record can reduce the likelihood of vulnerabilities being introduced.

(ii) Decentralized Storage Security: Implementing strong encryption techniques ensures that even if the data is accessed, it cannot be read without the appropriate decryption keys. Access control mechanisms can also be in place to restrict who can read or write to the blockchain, and all sensitive data should be encrypted before it is stored.

(iii) Key Management Solutions: The use of hardware security modules (HSMs) or secure enclaves to store and manage private keys can significantly improve security. Multi-factor authentication (MFA) and regular key rotation can further reduce the risk of key compromise.

(iv) Consensus Mechanism Enhancements: Using a permissioned blockchain model, where only trusted entities are allowed to participate in the consensus process, can mitigate these risks. In addition, the use of robust consensus algorithms that are resistant to such attacks can further increase security.

(v) Scalability and Performance Enhancements: Layer 2 scaling solutions, such as sidechains and off-chain transactions, can alleviate performance bottlenecks. Efficient consensus mechanisms and optimizing the blockchain's architecture for high throughput can also help address these issues.

(vi) Quantum-Resistant Cryptographic Integration: To mitigate the risks arising from advances in quantum computing, the blockchain and cryptography communities are actively researching and developing Quantum-Resistant Cryptographic (QRC) or PQC algorithms. These algorithms aim to ensure the security of blockchain systems even in a post-quantum computing era. However, implementing quantum-resistant cryptography in an SSI system would require the transition to new cryptographic standards and ensuring backward compatibility with existing systems.

(vii) Optimization of polynomial multiplication: Additional techniques such as Toom-Cook method can also be used within PQC algorithms. The Toom-Cook method is an algorithm for fast multiplication and can be generalized to more than two operands. It can also be used in classical computing to speed up the multiplication of polynomials and integers. The basic idea of the Toom-Cook method is to break down the input operands into smaller pieces, perform intermediate multiplications, and then combine the results to obtain the final product. The decisive innovation lies in the choice of a suitable "splitting point" for the decomposition of the operands. The method is particularly effective when it comes to operands of higher degree, which makes it advantageous for the multiplication of polynomials.

The algorithms of PQC, on the other hand, focus on cryptographic methods that are assumed

Fig. 4: A quantum attack to a BCN-SSI architecture a) Eve with quantum computer can attack the transactions on BCN-SSI b) PQC algorithm prevents Eve’s quantum attack.

to be secure against attacks from quantum computers. Therefore, the Toom-Cook multiplication method, although not directly related to the quantum resistant aspects of PQC, can be used within PQC algorithms so that it can play a role in optimizing the efficiency of the underlying mathematical operations. Their use can usually be at a lower level, providing efficient implementations for certain mathematical operations that are not directly related to the cryptographic aspects of PQC. First of all, efficient multiplication methods are crucial for the efficiency of the implementation of many cryptographic algorithms, as they often involve large integer or polynomial operations. For this reason, Toom-Cook multiplication method can be used to optimize the performance of basic arithmetic operations, such as polynomial multiplication or modular arithmetic, which are common in PQC algorithms. Second, although the multiplication methods themselves are not directly related to PQC, they can be used in the implementation of certain PQC algorithms.

VI. SIMULATION RESULTS

A. Experimental Setup

In our computation time experimentation, we selected Kubernetes and leveraged its Central Processing Unit (CPU) Management Control Policy (MCP) feature, as outlined in Kubernetes v1.12’s documentation on Control CPU Management Policies on the Node ⁽¹⁾. MCP helps

¹Online: <https://kubernetes.io/docs/tasks/administer-cluster/cpu-management-policies/>, Available: January 2024.

Fig. 5: Illustration of the experimental testbed with VMs and PQC containers.

manage and allocate computational resources efficiently in our experimental setup. Kubernetes routinely monitored the CPU cores' load status, and the allocation of the five CPU cores was managed by the MCP. The testing environment consisted of separate workstations, each equipped with 48 CPU cores and 64 GB of memory. Despite the nodes' robust capabilities, the tests were intentionally restricted to using only five of the available CPU cores. The nodes featured a Level 1 (L1) cache of 768 kiB, a Level 2 (L2) cache of 24 miB, and a Level 3 (L3) cache of 33 miB. The computational applications for PQC were containerized within Docker, with each distinct computation method housed in its respective container. In our system, while specific PQC algorithms (such as CRYSTALS-KYBER and CRYSTALS-Dilithium) were not used, we focused on the general principles of PQC methods that uses high order polynomial multiplication in their algorithms. For example, in the Kyber.CPAPKE encryption scheme (which is a public key encryption scheme stage of CRYSTALS-Kyber [32]), encryption involves generating the ciphertext using an error polynomial and product dot multiplication with a public matrix.

While decryption involves recovering the original message from the ciphertext using the error polynomial and the appropriate secret polynomial, the Toom-Cook multiplication method as a PQC computation method is used to optimizes mathematical operations. The Toom-Cook method also allows for more opportunities for parallelization compared to the schoolbook method. This means some of the sub-problems generated by Toom-Cook can be computed simultaneously on multiple cores or processors, further accelerating the PQC algorithm. The Toom-Cook method

was executed both on a single CPU core and through parallel programming across all five CPU cores, capitalizing on the inherent advantage of Toom-Cook in parallel processing, as highlighted by [33]. The experimental testbed is depicted in Fig. 5.

For the implementation of the DIM platform, we used the OpenStack platform in our test configuration to instantiate two virtual machines. One of the virtual machines hosted a Representational State Transfer (REST) Application Programming Interface (API), while the other hosted a DID system that used Hyperledger Indy as the underlying DID blockchain. The DID Virtual Machine (VM) boasted 8 GB of RAM, 4 virtual CPUs, and a 40 GB disk space allocation. Within this DID VM, four container nodes were designated as issuers, and a Flask-based REST API was implemented to enable users to submit requests to the BCN, facilitating various identity and credential management operations. Users could interact with the implemented API to request credentials, perform verification, manage their identities, securely authenticate themselves, and control access to their identity information. The communication protocol employed for interactions with the terms of service was the DIDComm messaging protocol from the Hyperledger Aries project². This protocol is distinguished by robust features such as strong encryption, privacy-friendly attributes, and provenance verification, facilitating secure communication between nodes. The system is able to manage client credentials and identities and ensure the confidentiality, integrity and authenticity of identity-related messages exchanged within the system, thanks to the DIDComm protocol.

Note that the experimental setup described above can be applied within the O-RAN architecture to improve resource sharing. The combination of containerization, virtualization, secure communication protocols and efficient computation methods is in line with the principles of O-RAN and promotes flexibility, scalability and dynamic resource usage in the RAN. The use of Kubernetes and its CPU MCP feature is crucial in O-RAN for dynamic resource allocation and efficient use of computing resources. Kubernetes can manage and allocate CPU cores according to the requirements of various O-RAN functions, such as baseband processing, beamforming and other radio access tasks. The Toom-Cook multiplication method, especially when implemented with parallel processing on multiple CPU cores, can improve the computational efficiency of resource-intensive operations within the O-RAN architecture. For example, complex signal processing tasks in beamforming and channel coding can benefit from parallel processing with Toom-Cook

²Online: <https://github.com/hyperledger/aries>, Available: January 2024

TABLE II
AVERAGE VALUES AND STANDARD DEVIATIONS OF EXPERIMENTAL DID IMPLEMENTATION
FOR CREDENTIAL OPERATIONS

KPI (time, msec)	20 Clients (mean \pm SD)	30 Clients (mean \pm SD)	50 Clients (mean \pm SD)
Credential Presentation	2.00 \pm 0.15	2.04 \pm 0.11	2.04 \pm 0.10
Credential Offer	34.8 \pm 0.84	35.2 \pm 0.84	35.2 \pm 0.84
DIDcomm Connection Creation	43.8 \pm 0.84	44.0 \pm 0.71	44.0 \pm 0.71
DIDcomm Signing	5.00 \pm 0.16	5.04 \pm 0.11	5.04 \pm 0.11
DIDcomm Revoke Credential	14.8 \pm 0.84	15.2 \pm 0.84	15.2 \pm 0.84

when PQC algorithms are used. The DID implementation contributes to secure communication within the O-RAN environment by using the DIDComm message protocol.

In O-RAN, secure communication is essential for the exchange of control plane information, configuration data and other sensitive data between different RAN elements and network functions. The use of OpenStack for the creation of VMs and the management of virtualized infrastructures is in line with the virtualization principles of O-RAN. Virtualization allows RAN functions to be deployed in isolated environments, enabling efficient scaling, resource isolation and dynamic allocation of computing resources. The containerization of the PQC computation application with Docker enables the modular use of different computational tasks. This modular approach is in line with the O-RAN architecture’s goal of disaggregation, which enables the deployment of specific functions as needed and facilitates the sharing of resources across different network slices. The Flask-based REST API, implemented for DID operations, can be used in O-RAN for interaction between different RAN elements. This API can facilitate the exchange of identity-related information, authentication and authorization requests.

B. DID Implementation Results

Table II shows average values and standard deviations for various Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) in an experimental implementation of a DID system, with a focus on credential operations. The KPIs are measured in milliseconds and the average times are given for different credential-related activities with different numbers of clients (20, 30 and 50) targeting the use of shared resources (e.g. users/MNOs). In this context, “clients” refers to entities (users, MNOs, or devices) interacting with the DID system to perform various credential operations.

Average Credential Presentation: The average time for credential presentation is approximately 2 milliseconds. This KPI indicates the time it takes to present a credential, an essential

operation in identity systems for authentication or authorization. The low average time indicates an efficient and fast process, which is crucial for the usability and responsiveness of the system.

Average Credential Offer: The average time for credential offer is around 35 milliseconds. This KPI indicates the time required to offer an access authorization that includes the release of or access to identity-related information. The slightly higher time compared to offering credentials can be attributed to additional steps in the creation and offering of credentials. However, the average time is still reasonable for most practical applications.

Average DIDcomm Connection Creation: The average time required to establish a DIDcomm connection is around 44 milliseconds. DIDcomm is a message protocol used in decentralized identity systems. This KPI reflects the time it takes to establish connections between entities using DIDcomm. The efficiency of this process is crucial for secure and timely communication within the decentralized identity ecosystem.

Average DIDcomm Signing: The average time for DIDcomm signing is about 5 milliseconds. This KPI measures the time it takes to perform cryptographic signing operations within the DIDcomm protocol. Fast signing times are important to maintain the responsiveness of identity systems, especially in scenarios where frequent cryptographic operations are required.

Average DIDcomm Revoke Credential: The average time for revoking a credential in the DIDcomm context is about 15 milliseconds. The revocation of credentials is an important process in identity systems for managing the validity of credentials. The specified average time indicates an efficient credential revocation process that contributes to the overall security and reliability of decentralized identity implementation.

To summarize, the average values in the table show that the experimental DID implementation for credential operations works efficiently and adequately for several key activities. Credential presentation and DIDcomm signing have particularly fast processing times, while offering credentials, establishing DIDcomm connections, and revoking credentials require additional steps or computation, resulting in slightly longer average times. These metrics are important to evaluate the feasibility and effectiveness of the decentralized identity system and to ensure that it meets the requirements of real-world use cases with a varying number of clients sharing some resources.

C. Calculation Methods in PQC

Fig. 6, Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 provide a performance comparison of computational methods that can be used within the PQC computational algorithm, focusing on Toom Cook with 5 CPU cores

under different computational loads. The load ratio, which indicates the computational load on four busy CPU cores (%), is varied from 0 to 70 percent, and the corresponding execution times for each method are recorded. In Fig. 6 with credential presentation (as step-3 and step-4 of Fig. 2), the computation time for this task increases steadily with the rise in the load ratio, starting at 0.019 seconds and reaching 0.050 seconds at 70%. Fig. 6 with credential offer (as step-1 and step-2 of Fig. 2), is similar to Credential Presentation. The time required for Credential Offer also shows a gradual upward trend with the increasing load ratio. The computation time ranges from 0.052 seconds at 0% load to 0.083 seconds at 70%. This suggests a proportional increase in processing time as the system experiences higher demand. At the same time, the time for offering the credential is higher than the time for presenting the credential, which indicates that the additional steps for offering the credential are involved.

Fig. 6: Total Computation for a PQC computation method with 5 CPU cores for credential presentation and offer versus load ratio

In Fig. 7 with DIDcomm Connection, the total computation time follows a similar pattern, incrementing from 0.006 seconds at 0% load to 0.09 seconds at 70%. In Fig. 7 with DIDcomm Signing exhibits a similar trend, with the computation time gradually increasing from 0.02 seconds at no load to 0.053 seconds at a load ratio of 70%. This indicates that the time required to establish DIDcomm connections and cryptographic signing operations increases proportionally when the system encounters a higher computational load. This shows that the computational effort for the revocation of credentials in the context of DIDcomm increases proportionally to the system load. The longest time to establish a DIDcomm connection indicates that establishing secure communication channels between entities incurs some overhead, which contributes to an increase in processing time compared to other operations.

Fig. 7: Total Computation for a PQC computation method with 5 CPU cores for DIDcomm connection and DIDcomm signing versus load ratio

In Fig. 8 with DIDcomm Revoke, the computation time experiences a consistent rise from 0.03 seconds to 0.063 seconds across the range of load ratios. This shows that the computational effort for the revocation of credentials in the context of DIDcomm increases proportionally to the system load. The average time to revoke a credential with DIDcomm is longer than the time for DIDcomm signing of Fig. 7, suggesting that the revocation process requires additional complexity or computation compared to cryptographic signing.

Fig. 8: Total computation time for a PQC computation method with 5 CPU cores with DIDcomm revoke operation versus load ratio.

The observed trends in computation times across these tasks suggest a direct correlation between the load ratio and the processing time. When the system experiences higher demand, the Toom-Cook method exhibits incremental computation times for credential-related operations and DIDcomm tasks, highlighting the importance of load management and resource optimization for

maintaining efficient performance in decentralized identity systems. The Toom-Cook algorithm seems to provide stable and efficient performance at different computational loads, especially when using multiple cores. These results show how important it is to consider the computational load and the number of CPU cores when selecting a suitable multiplication algorithm for PQC.

VII. DISCUSSIONS, LIMITATIONS AND POSSIBLE SOLUTIONS

A. *Discussions on Energy Consumption Aspects of Post Quantum Cryptography*

Although Toom-Cook is not explicitly studied in the context of energy efficiency in this paper, the broader study of energy efficiency in PQC methods encompasses the landscape of mathematical algorithms used in cryptographic operations. NIST has recently standardized CRYSTALS-KYBER for key exchange and public key encryption and CRYSTALS-Dilithium for digital signatures. With the advent of new PQC methods, the energy footprint of these PQC methods and their comparison with RSA and ECC is examined in detail in [34]. The authors show that the best PQC methods can beat elliptic curve and RSA methods for a TLS 1.3 handshake connections. If the energy consumption is compared with RSA+Elliptic Curve Diffie–Hellman Ephemeral (ECDHE) and ECDSA+ECDHE, Dilithium+Kyber and Falcon+Kyber are generally much more efficient than RSA+ECDHE. On the other hand, only Dilithium and Kyber outperform ECDSA+ECHDE. At the same time, the performance of all PQC methods (except Sphincs+ and Kyber) is quite good compared to existing key exchange methods. Toom-Cook, which is known for its efficiency in polynomial multiplication, could potentially be part of the PQC methods that are studied for their computational and energy efficiency.

B. *Limitations and Possible Solutions*

There are also some limitations that should be considered for BCN-based SSI technology for resource sharing in O-RAN. Here are a few limitations and possible solutions:

(i) Malicious Users/Operators: The above process assumes that the SSI registration mechanism would deter malicious users/MNOs from participating in the resource sharing process. However, it is still possible for malicious entities to join the system and disrupt the resource sharing. A reputation system can be introduced to assign reputation scores based on behavior, accuracy of models, contribution, and adherence to the protocol. Users/MNOs with low reputation scores can be excluded or given limited access, mitigating the risk of malicious behavior.

TABLE III
O-RAN AUTHENTICATION COMPARISON WITH SSI AND REGULAR BLOCKCHAIN

Category	Certificate-based Device Authentication	BCN-based Authentication	BCN-based SSI	PQC BCN based SSI
Characteristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Authenticate an O- CU, O-DU and O-RU during certificate enrollment with a CA server. — Use CA signed X.509 certificates to authenticate before communicating — Enrollment procedure in compliance with 3GPP with the CA server to obtain an operator certificate. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Uses blockchain’s distributed ledger technology and authentication methods to enhance the privacy and security. — Authentication relies on public-private key pairs stored on the blockchain. — Users does not have direct control over their identity and personal data. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —Managing digital identities in which individual O-RAN devices have sole ownership over the ability to control their data. — Authentication and ID management rely on BCN, decentralized and tamper-resistant infrastructure for storing and managing identities and credentials. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —Using cryptographic algorithms that are secure against a cryptanalytic attack by a quantum computer. — Implemented on classical, non-quantum computing O-RAN platforms for higher security level against quantum computer threats.
Advantages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — The identity of the O-RAN device is verified by a trusted third party. — Easy to specify whether all or some certificates issued by a specific CA should be trusted. — Explicitly deactivate trust for self-signed certificate of a network sharing partner. — Easy implementation and administration to issue certificates for new O-RAN devices and renew certificates. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Enhanced security, transparency, immutability, and potential for decentralized governance. — In O-RAN, transparency can help network operators and regulators monitor network activities and ensure compliance with regulations. — Depending on the BCN’s governance model, O-RAN networks may benefit from decentralized decision-making, reducing reliance on centralized authorities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Information is stored in a secure decentralised manner, reducing the risk of fraudulent activities. — MNOs can choose what to reveal and keep private by controlling their device information. — O-RAN device credentials can be verified any time regardless of whether or not the issuer still exists or online. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —Secure against attacks from both classical and quantum computers. — Developing more secure communication protocols and systems that can leverage the power of quantum computing and even protect against them. — Maintain secure and private communication, preventing malicious entities from breaching data privacy.
Limitations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — A centralized source for posting and obtaining information about certificates and information about revoked certificates. — A compromised, corrupted, or revoked CA can undermine the trust and validity of the certificates it issued. — Attackers can issue fake certificates for legitimate O-RAN devices, which can be used to carry out man-in-the-middle attacks and steal sensitive information. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Costly to implement blockchain in a network sharing scenario that the capital-intensive investment deters from adopting the technology. — In O-RAN, this exposure could potentially reveal sensitive information about network interactions, which may not be desirable in some scenarios. — Regular BCN-based authentication may expose certain transaction details on the public ledger, potentially impacting privacy in O-RAN. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Lack of standardization and integration aspects for O-RAN. — May not be compatible with all existing network sharing applications and systems. — Adoption of BCN-based SSI may depend on the availability and performance of the underlying blockchain infrastructure. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —Public key infrastructure for O-RAN devices must support new certificate types. — May need to upgrade the infrastructure to support transition to PQC. — Vulnerability analysis of quantum-resistant cryptography to advancements in quantum technology is a very long-term problem

(ii) Privacy and Security: The usage of BCN makes it challenging to double-check calculations and detect malicious clients. Solutions like resource sharing with differential privacy [35], adversarial robustness, secure multi-party computation, homomorphic encryption, and secure enclaves can enhance privacy, integrity, and confidentiality of the resource sharing process. These techniques protect against attacks, ensure secure aggregation, and prevent manipulation.

(iii) Scalability: As the number of users and network nodes increases, the BCN must handle a higher volume of transactions and identity verifications. The use of BCN in resource sharing can

introduce scalability issues due to the consensus requirement before each iteration. Consensus algorithms designed for scalability, such as Proof of Stake (PoS) or Byzantine Fault Tolerance (BFT), can be employed to optimize the consensus process, reduce computational overhead, and minimize message exchange. Additionally, implementing Layer 2 solutions like sidechains or off-chain transactions can alleviate the load on the main blockchain, thereby improving scalability. Another approach is sharding, in which the blockchain network is partitioned into smaller, easier-to-manage segments (shards). Each shard processes a subset of transactions independently, allowing the network to process multiple transactions in parallel, increasing overall throughput.

(iv) Storage and Performance: Storing large-scale resource sharing data directly on the BCN ledger can impact scalability and performance. Storing only one file validator (CRC) on the BCN while transferring log information directly between clients/MNOs and the BCN can reduce storage requirements and improve scalability.

(v) Fastest Algorithm: Although Toom-Cook is efficient for certain input sizes, it is not always the fastest multiplication algorithm for all scenarios. Other algorithms may outperform Toom-Cook for certain input ranges or hardware configurations. A hybrid approach that dynamically selects the multiplication algorithm based on the input size, or even considers multiple algorithms in parallel and selects the fastest result, can be explored.

(vi) Large Scale Deployments: The computational requirements for maintaining the blockchain, performing identity verification, and executing smart contracts will be increased with large scale deployments. These operations demand significant processing power and energy, potentially leading to higher operational costs. Employing energy-efficient cryptographic algorithms, such as those optimized for post-quantum security, can reduce the computational load. The Toom-Cook algorithm, while efficient for certain input sizes, may not always be optimal. A hybrid approach that dynamically selects the most efficient algorithm based on input size and hardware configuration can optimize computational resources.

(vii) Economic Impact: The economic costs of deploying and maintaining a large-scale BCN-based SSI system include infrastructure expenses, energy consumption and ongoing maintenance. The use of permissioned blockchains can help reduce these costs by limiting participation to trusted entities, thereby reducing overall computational load and energy consumption.

Finally, Table III provides a comparative analysis between SSI-based and regular BCN-based authentication methods for O-RAN adoption.

C. Future Work

The proposed BCN-based DIM system for O-RAN can achieve enhanced security, privacy, and efficiency by incorporating advanced security mechanisms. The integration of machine learning models for anomaly detection or potential security breaches [36], privacy-preserving techniques for data protection [37], and fine-grained searchable encryption for access control [38] can significantly strengthens the system's ability to resist quantum attacks and manage identity data securely. These enhancements can also provide a comprehensive and robust security framework that addresses the challenges of large-scale deployment in real-world O-RAN scenarios. Also note that although we have used Toom-Cook in our evaluations, it is not the only method that can be used. Other algorithms such as Karatsuba multiplication and even faster algorithms such as Schonhage-Strassen multiplication can also be used depending on the specific PQC scheme.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents and explores the integration of post-quantum blockchain-based DIM into the O-RAN architecture to provide a secure, efficient and adaptable solution for identity verification and resource sharing in the dynamic landscape of O-RAN. An in-depth examination of the role of BCN-SSI in the O-RAN created a robust system architecture that delineates the responsibilities of users and mobile network operators. The detailed authentication process ensures secure and reliable identity management within the O-RAN ecosystem. Spectrum sharing is shown to demonstrate the proposed DIM framework's versatility in secure resource sharing. Additionally, we addressed quantum threats by exploring PQC methods to enhance the system's resilience against potential attacks. Implementing a post-quantum BCN-based SSI solution in O-RAN with multiple MNOs and users enhances identity management, secure authentication, access control, auditing, and data privacy in the post-quantum era. Comprehensive simulations validate the effectiveness of the DIM implementation, providing valuable insights. Discussions on energy consumption and limitations offer a better understanding, paving the way for future optimizations and enhancements.

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